

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF NEW INHIBITORS AND RESEARCH OF THEIR PROPERTIES

Kamilov T.

Master's student of the Tashkent Chemical-Technological Institute

Kholikova S.

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Tashkent Chemical-Technological Institute

Ziyadullayeva K.

Chiqchik State Pedagogical institute of Tashkent region

ABSTRACT

Convenient methods have been developed for the synthesis of corrosion inhibitors based on available local raw materials in the process of condensation of Croton aldehyde with ammonia under normal conditions. The optimal conditions for the process have been established.

Keywords: corrosion inhibitor, oil production, croton fraction, ammonia, condensation.

Introduction: Corrosion control of gas production and transport equipment is carried out by various methods: by applying anti-corrosion insulation, by means of electrochemical protection, by using special grades of steels, inhibitors, etc. The demand of the Republic for corrosion and scale inhibitors is more than 5 thousand tons per year. Due to the lack of production of corrosion and scale inhibitors, the latter are imported from other countries for foreign currency.

The chemical industry is well developed in Uzbekistan. Ammonia, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, urea, triourea, they can serve as potential raw materials for the production of corrosion and scale inhibitors, are large-tonnage products of the chemical industry of the Republic. In this regard, the development of convenient one-stage methods for the synthesis of corrosion and scale inhibitors based on local raw materials is highly relevant.

There are many known methods of combating corrosion. Of these, four main groups can be distinguished. The first group of protection is used at the stage of metal production in the process of its metallurgical and mechanical processing. The general theory of alloying is based on three main factors that characterize the effectiveness of the corrosive element.

The corrosion rate can be reduced or prevented altogether by creating alloys that form a layer of corrosion products with high protective properties on their surface under the action of an aggressive environment. Alloying structural steels with copper-zinc and aluminum increases the protective properties of the surface layer and eliminates the possibility of the appearance of internal stresses in it [1].

Experimental technique: The second fundamentally different way to increase the corrosion resistance of a metal is the electrochemical method. In the process of dissolution of a metal on its surface, two electrode reactions occur simultaneously: anodic - dissolution of the metal and cathodic - reduction of the oxidizer. With significant contact of the metal with an aggressive medium, the corrosion process stabilizes and a stationary state occurs, characterized by the equality of the rates of the anodic and cathodic reactions ($j_a=j_k$) and the corresponding values of the potential Ecor, called the stationary potential. It follows

from the stationarity condition that, to slow down the rate of dissolution of the metal, it is sufficient to reduce the rate of at least one of the electrode reactions [2].

Results and discussion: Programs of target projects for the modernization and technical renewal of the basic sectors of our economy make it possible to introduce modern innovative technologies designed to give a powerful impetus to Uzbekistan's entry into new frontiers, ensuring the competitiveness of our country in the world market. The accelerated development of the oil and gas industry has an impact on scientific and technological progress in the field of engineering and technology of drilling, production, transportation and processing of oil and gas. The growth in the number of new gas, gas condensate and oil fields involved in the development, the commissioning of gas pipelines and compressor stations requires the use of cost-effective methods and technical means to prevent the phenomena of corrosive effects on downhole, field, transport equipment and pipelines. About 60 billion cubic meters of natural gas, about 8 million tons of oil and gas condensate are produced annually in Uzbekistan. Natural gas, gas condensate and oil contain highly corrosive components such as hydrogen sulfide (1-5% vol.) And carbon dioxide (0.5-6.0 %).

In world practice, cathodic protection is widespread in protection against marine or underground corrosion, where most of the metal structures, pipelines, etc. are subject to protection in one form or another. Magnesium alloys are used as soluble anodes and protectors to protect ferrous metals, less zinc and aluminum alloys. Cathodic protection with the use of anodes - protectors has its own inconveniences, since it requires rather frequent replacement of consumable protectors, which can sometimes become economically unprofitable.

Anodic protection is used to protect sections of chemical plants, which are made of metal that can be passivated in this environment. The method of anodic protection is promising, but requires the development of control over the mode of maintaining the required potential [4].

The third most versatile method of protecting

metals from corrosion is the application of both metallic and non-metallic coatings to the metal surface.

The main purpose of the protective coating is, on the one hand, to create a barrier layer that prevents the penetration of a corrosive medium to the metal surface, and on the other hand, to restrict or completely prevent the formation of a new phase of corrosion products at the metal-coating interface. The material of the protective coating, first of all, must have high chemical resistance, low permeability to water, gases, chlorine vapor, sulfate, etc., mechanical strength and structural stability [1].

Among protective metal coatings, zinc coatings account for the largest specific weight. Their main area of application is the protection of ferrous metal products from atmospheric corrosion. Zinc protects ferrous metals from corrosion not only mechanically as a coating, but also electromechanically acting as an anode. According to the materials used and the method of production, non-metallic coatings are subdivided into lining, rubber coating, paint and varnish and others [2]. Modern paints and varnishes are complex mixtures containing, in addition to a film-forming agent and a pigment, fillers such as surfactants, dispersants, thickeners, solvents and other additives. Paints and varnishes have a number of advantages over other types of protective coatings. The main disadvantages of paint and varnish coatings include their limited steam, gas and water permeability, as well as insuffi-

cient heat resistance [5]. The fourth group of methods of combating corrosion is the treatment of a corrosive environment by introducing corrosion inhibitors. The introduction of small amounts (no more than 1 %) of an inhibitor into a corrosive environment can lead to a significant decrease in the corrosion rate of metals. In this case, the corrosion inhibition coefficient, equal to the ratio of corrosion rates in the absence and in the presence of an inhibitor, reaches values of 1000 or more.

Currently known inhibitors can protect almost any metal in a wide variety of environments: air, aggressive gases, sea and fresh water, coolants, water mixtures, acids and alkalis.

The main advantages of using inhibitors, in addition to the simplicity of the technology, is the ability to use conventional carbon steels instead of expensive stainless steels, and in some cases the possibility of improving the mechanical properties of the metal. The use of inhibitors is justified for technological processes with circulation of limited volumes of corrosive liquids and under the condition of low losses, which determines the actual consumption of the inhibitor.

Numerous organic and inorganic compounds with at least one element with unpaired electrons in their molecule can serve as corrosion inhibitors. In the production of oil and gas treatment, dozens of names of large-tonnage chemical reagents are used.

Table 1

Until now, Uzbekneftegaz JSC uses the following chemicals:

№	Name	Brand	Quantity ton
1.	Water-soluble demulsifier	Dissolvan - 4411	100,0
2.	Oil-soluble demulsifier	Dissolvan – 3359, Brand K-1	160,0
3.	Gas Production Corrosion Inhibitor	Dodikor V - 4543	350,0
4.	Corrosion inhibitor for oil production	Dodikor V -4712	1150,0
5.	Scale inhibitor (concentrate)	Dodiscale V– 2570 K	400,0
6.	Antifoam (antifoam)	DanoxAF-200	100
7.	Fluorine containing foaming agent	Finiflan- A3 F/A	270
8.	Hydrocarbon foaming agent	Analogue– ПИО-6	10000
	Total		3530

Out of 8 positions, not a single chemical is produced in the Republic. In the Republic, JSC "Navoi-zot" produces methanol - 35 thousand tons per year; formaldehyde - 7 thousand tons per year; acetaldehyde - 200 thousand tons per year; acetic acid - 20 thousand tons per year, ammonia - more than 500 thousand tons/year. In the production of acetaldehyde, the so-called croton fraction is formed as a byproduct. In the amount of 800-3500 tons per year. Which is not processed but burned. The croton fraction has a trace. Composition % mass (average)

Crotonic aldehyde - 57,4-66,95

Paraldehyde -13,45-29,47

Acetone - 0,63-10,56

Water - rest

In the literature [6] there are data on the use of crotonaldehyde as an inhibitor of hydrogen sulfide corrosion. However, due to the high toxicity of crotonaldehyde (its MPC in the working area is 0.5 ng / m³), this inhibitor has not found industrial application. With the aim of using crotonic aldehyde, creating a waste-free technology and protecting the environment, we studied the condensation reaction of crotonaldehyde with ammonia monoethanolamine.

